

INTERFACE STRENGTH GRADATION IN THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES: A NEW APPROACH TO INCREASE THE DAMAGE TOLERANCE

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ABSTRACT

A new design has been developed for thermoplastic composites based on the gradation of the interlaminar interface strength (IGIS). IGIS laminates have been prepared by properly alternating layers of a woven fabric with layers of compatibilized and not compatibilized polypropylene films configured symmetrically or asymmetrically with respect to the middle plane by means of the well-known film stacking technique. Maleated PP has been used to compatibilize the polypropylene with glass fibres and thus to manage the interface strength layer by layer.

The flexural and low-velocity impact characterizations showed that the presence of the coupling agent, through the strengthening of the matrix/fibre interface, improved the quasi-static flexural properties in conventional composite structures (prepared with fully compatibilized polymeric layers) but considerably lowered the low velocity impact resistance of the composite, in terms of maximum load before fibre breakage and recovered energy after the impact. The use of the IGIS design, which grades the interface strength through the laminate thickness, allowed to prepare composites with a favourable combination of flexural properties and impact resistance. Moreover, the IGIS design proved to be more effective in preserving the integrity of the composite after low velocity impacts. The post-impact flexural characterization performed on samples impacted at 6 J and 25 J, showed that some of the IGIS laminates have better damage tolerance with respect to the fully compatibilized laminate as the flexural response decreased to a minor extent.

Acoustic emission (AE) was applied to obtain more information about the level of damage and the failure modes occurred at the different impact energies. The AE signals were recorded in real time during flexural tests on both non-impacted and impacted specimens. The several configurations exhibited different behaviours in terms of acoustic emission activity and AE signal features, such as amplitude and duration, which allowed the identification of the mechanisms responsible of impact energy absorption. The role played by the compression side of the samples was pointed out along with the effective role of IGIS design in tailoring the strength where it is needed thus providing an overall better damage tolerance.

1 INTRODUCTION

Continuous fibre reinforced thermoplastic matrix composites have gained an outstanding interest mainly because of their fast processability, high impact and delamination strength, chemical resistance, low moisture absorption, unlimited shelf life of raw materials, low cost and recyclability with respect to thermosetting based systems [1,2]. In this frame, isotactic polypropylene (PP) is considered one of the most promising thermoplastic matrix for many industrial applications. The reinforcement by unidirectional fibres or, better, woven fabrics enhances PP mechanical properties as

stiffness and fracture resistance and limits the material deformation under creep loads [3–5].

Focusing the attention on composite laminates, generally suitable for structural applications, it is well established that these systems are very susceptible to low-velocity impact events. These latter, often occurring accidentally during the service life of composite structures, cause various damages, such as matrix cracks, delamination and fibre breakage, very difficult to be detected by naked eyes and leading to significant reductions in the strength and stiffness of the materials.

Given the typical brittle behaviour of structures obtained by stacking of matrix and reinforcement layers, largely used in civil engineering constructions and transportation fields, extensive investigations have been performed to understand involved mechanisms of impact damages and, consequently, to ensure an adequate durability of these component performances. The impact behaviour of composite laminates depends on many factors as interface properties, laminate thickness, preform architecture and sequence lay-up. An appropriate optimization of these laminate parameters improves the damage resistance and tolerance of these items. In this regard, hybridization approach has been demonstrated to be a very effective way to balance stiffness and toughness and improve the impact energy absorbing capability of composite laminate systems [6–9].

After low-velocity impacts, an area of interest is the effect of damage on the mechanical properties of laminated composite structures, thus assessing what is generally known as damage tolerance. An understanding of damage tolerance can be gained through experiments that commonly involve compression testing of impacted laminates. Compression is critical for impact-damaged specimens because under this type of loading the strength reductions are the largest. Even though composite materials are often used in applications where they are subjected to bending, the residual flexural strength has received relatively little attention but with an increasing trend in the last years [10–13]. In this study four point bending tests were used as a post-impact evaluation tool. In addition, these tests were monitored by acoustic emission in an attempt to identify and discriminate the failure modes of the different configurations. AE, defined as the class of phenomena where transient elastic waves are generated by the rapid release of energy from localized sources within a material, is capable of detecting the dynamic processes associated to the degradation of structural integrity and therefore can be used to monitor in situ a structure during loading. AE has been applied virtually on all classes of materials and a great number of mechanisms responsible of AE have been identified especially in composite materials including: fibre failure, debonding at fibre/matrix interface, plastic deformation and matrix cracks, delamination, friction between fibres and matrix.

In this contribution, a new design of hybridization based on the gradation of the interlaminar interface strength (IGIS) has been proposed (Figure 1). Film-stacked samples are validated in terms of flexural and low-velocity impact tests as well as by real time acoustic emission technique to achieve insights about damage mechanisms occurring at different impact energies.

Figure 1 Schematics of the IGIS laminate design and comparison with some conventional laminate hybridization schemes.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

The polypropylene used was the MA712 grade supplied by Unipetrol – Czech Republic (MFI = 12 g/10 min; referred to as “N”). Polypropylene grafted with maleic anhydride, commercialized under the trade name Polybond 3200 (MFI = 115 g/10 min, 1 wt% maleic anhydride; from Chemtura, Philadelphia - PA, USA) was used at 2.0% by weight as coupling agent to improve the fibre/matrix interface. Compatibilized matrix has been referred to as “C”. Finally, a plain weave type glass woven fabric (E-type glass fibres having density of 2.54 g/cm³, functionalized by amino silane groups) with a specific mass of 204 g/m² has been used as reinforcing fabric.

2.2 Sample preparation

Films of neat or compatibilized polypropylene having a thickness equal to 35-40 µm were prepared by using a film blowing extrusion line model Teach-Line E 20 T from Collin GmbH (Ebersberg, Germany). Composite laminates were produced by using the film stacking technique by means of a compression moulding machine (model P300P, Collin GmbH, Ebersberg, Germany). Twenty one layers of polypropylene films and twenty of glass woven fabric were alternatively stacked according to the specific stacking sequence (Table 1) as schematized in Figure 1, and heated according to opportune temperature and pressure profiles by using a laboratory press [4]. Samples consisting of 20 balanced fabric layers 0°/90°, symmetrically arranged with respect to the middle plane of the laminate ((0/90)₁₀s configuration), were produced with a target thickness of 3.30 mm and a glass fibre content of 45% by volume. The volume percentages of fibre and matrix were evaluated according to the ASTM D 3171 and ASTM D792, respectively.

Sample	Polymeric Layer Sequence
NEAT	20 N
COMP	20 C
HNC	10 N/10 C
HCN	10 C/10 N
HNCN	5 N/10 C/5 N
HCNC	5 C/10 N/5 C
HX	2 C/5 N/6 C/5 N/2 C

Table 1 Coding of IGIS laminates and layer sequences (N = not compatibilized PP layer; C = compatibilized PP layer; H = IGIS hybridized matrix sequence).

2.3 Characterization techniques

Optical analyses were performed in reflection mode by using a microscope (BX51 from Olympus, Japan) to investigate the fibres impregnation in the composite. The surface of all observed samples was preliminarily treated with a wet sandpaper and then polished with a very fine polishing paste. Fibre wetting was investigated by analysing fractured surfaces with a field emission scanning electron microscope (model QUANTA-200FEG from FEI – Eindhoven, The Netherlands). The examined surfaces were preliminarily coated with a thin layer of a gold-palladium alloy prior to SEM analysis.

Four-point bending tests have been performed on three specimens (170 mm × 60 mm) for each configuration in accordance with ASTM D 6272. This unusual width has been chosen in order to be sure of accommodating the whole impact damaged area, thus minimizing the edge effects. The distance between the loading noses (the load span) was one half of the support span (80 mm). A cross-head speed of 2.5 mm/min was used. Specimens have been tested in bending either after their production (non-impacted samples) or after the low-velocity impact tests (6J and 25J sample series) to measure their residual flexural strength. Mechanical tests have been performed on a Z010 from Zwick/Roell (Ulm, Germany) universal testing machine equipped with a 10 kN load cell.

Low-velocity impact tests were conducted using an instrumented drop-weight impact testing machine (model Fractovis Plus from CEAST – Italy) equipped with a hemispherical tip (diameter 12.7 mm). All tests were performed putting the sample on a stainless steel annular ring (internal diameter 40 mm, outer diameter 60 mm) and using two impact energies (6 J, 25 J). A minimum of 4 samples for each composition, measuring 80 mm x 80 mm and cut from the prepared laminates, were tested and their mean values and variance were calculated.

Pre- and post-impact flexural tests have been monitored by acoustic emission until final fracture occurred using an AMSY-5 AE system by Vallen Systeme GmbH (Icking, Germany). The AE acquisition settings used throughout this experimental work are as follows: threshold = 35 dB, Rearm Time (RT) = 0.4 ms, Duration Discrimination Time (DDT) = 0.2 ms and total gain = 34 dB. This threshold level has been defined from a 30 minutes track record of the background noise, with the AE setup configuration actually used, and has been set 6 dB above the maximum level of the recorded spurious signal from the electronic system. Two broad-band (100-1500 kHz, Fujicera 1045S) PZT AE sensors have been used. The sensors have been placed on the surface of the specimens at both ends to allow linear localization, with silicone grease as coupling agent.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Physical properties of laminates

Laminates showed physical properties close to the target values (Table 2). Their thickness was within the $\pm 10\%$ of the target value, the lowest and highest thickness being exhibited by the COMP and the NEAT samples, respectively. The fibre volume content was within $\pm 10\%$ of the target value. Composites sections were checked to detect the presence of voids within fibre bundles or in the matrix. From several acquisitions no voids were detected and all bundles appeared to be well impregnated by the hosting matrix. Tests were also performed to measure the percentage of voids with digestion methodology and results were all below the required 2% limit of acceptance.

<i>Sample</i>	<i>Thickness (mm)</i>	<i>Density (g/cm³)</i>	<i>V_f (%)</i>	<i>Voids Content (%)</i>
NEAT	3.63 ± 0.04	1.59 ± 0.01	42.1 ± 0.5	0.8 ± 0.3
COMP	3.05 ± 0.03	1.73 ± 0.01	49.9 ± 0.3	0.3 ± 0.2
HNC	3.43 ± 0.03	1.63 ± 0.01	45.2 ± 0.6	0.4 ± 0.2
HCN	3.12 ± 0.02	1.63 ± 0.01	45.3 ± 0.4	0.4 ± 0.2
HNCN	3.14 ± 0.02	1.63 ± 0.01	47.5 ± 0.7	0.4 ± 0.2
HCNC	3.41 ± 0.02	1.67 ± 0.01	45.7 ± 0.4	0.5 ± 0.2
HX	3.30 ± 0.03	1.67 ± 0.01	47.2 ± 0.5	0.6 ± 0.2

Table 2 Physical properties of laminates (fibre volume and voids content calculated according to the ASTM D3171 standard).

SEM morphological analysis, performed on fractured surfaces of laminates, is reported in Figure 2. The composite prepared with not compatibilized polymeric layers (NEAT micrograph in Figure 2) showed very long protruding fibres, which hinder the distinction of the different reinforcing layers. The poor fibre/polymer interface, allowing the slippage of fibres during the laminate deflection, delocalizes the fibres breakage. On the contrary, in fully compatibilized laminates (COMP micrograph in Figure 2) fibres bundles are clearly distinguished: very short fibres protrude from the fractured surface and often the fracture sharply passes through the bundle. This is an evidence that, during the laminate failure, crack propagation through fibres in compatibilized layers is very fast and straight through the laminate. These opposite behaviours are visible in IGIS laminates, where characteristic fibres fracture surfaces of neat and compatibilized layers can be identified and associated to the stacking sequence. Exploiting the interface strength gradation through the thickness, shown in Figure 2, induces unexpected structural behaviours, as shown in the following.

Figure 2 SEM micrographs of fractured samples showing the different fibre wetting through the laminate thickness in standard and IGIS composites. The two colours qualitatively show the sequence of neat and compatibilized layers [14].

3.2 Low-velocity impact tests

The low velocity impact characterization of NEAT and COMP laminates showed an opposite behaviour with respect to the static four point bending test (reported in the following). At low impact energy $E_i = 6$ J (Table 3) COMP laminate showed a higher peak load (4045 N) and a higher recovered energy (3.0 J) with respect to NEAT laminate (3732 N and 2.6 J, respectively) in accordance with the higher stiffness of the composite structure (Figure 3A and Figure 4A). The recovered energy represents the amount of energy elastically stored by the composite structure and then returned after the impact. It is calculated as the difference between the impact energy and the total energy absorbed during the impact event, thus higher recovered energy means lower irreversible mechanical phenomena. Since the impact energy was the same for all samples, higher values of the recovered energy are a direct evidence of lower damages induced in the composite structure through dissipating phenomena like matrix cracking, fibre slipping and delaminations. The compatibilized laminate dissipated 50 % of the impact energy versus the 57 % of the NEAT laminate meaning that it incurred in lower damaging. IGIS laminates showed intermediate results in the same impact conditions, with the HNCN laminate showing the best result among them. In fact, it exhibited a peak load of 3923 N and a recovered energy of 2.9 J (3 % lower than that of the COMP configuration). The highest peak displacement, which is the maximum deflection of the laminate during the impact event, was exhibited by the NEAT laminate. Almost all IGIS configurations behaved as the COMP composite in terms of peak and residual displacements, showing comparable external damages.

Sample	Peak Load (N)	Peak Displacement (mm)	Absorbed Energy (J)	Recovered Energy (J)	Residual Displacement (mm)
NEAT	3732±92	2.8±0.2	3.4±0.1	2.6±0.1	0.6±0.1
COMP	4045±65	2.7±0.1	3.0±0.1	3.0±0.1	0.5±0.1
HNC	3854±68	2.7±0.1	3.2±0.1	2.8±0.1	0.5±0.1
HCN	3732±57	2.8±0.1	3.3±0.1	2.7±0.1	0.5±0.1
HNCN	3923±62	2.7±0.1	3.1±0.1	2.9±0.1	0.5±0.1
HCNC	3871±72	2.7±0.1	3.2±0.1	2.8±0.1	0.5±0.1
HX	3836±97	2.7±0.2	3.3±0.1	2.7±0.1	0.5±0.1

Table 3 Average value and variance of main parameters evaluated from impact tests performed at 6 J

As the impact energy rose to $E_i = 25$ J (Table 4), the NEAT laminate behaved better than COMP laminate exhibiting both higher peak load (8035 N versus 6631 N, +21 %) and recovered energy (10.1 J versus 7.5 J, +34 %). The jagged shape trend after the force peak in the Force vs Displacement curve at $E_i = 25$ J is a direct evidence that the COMP configuration incurred in fibres breakage unlike the NEAT laminate (Figure 3B). The higher peak displacement confirmed its lower strength and capability to recover elastic energy (Figure 4B). Although the use of IGIS layered configurations allowed to obtain impact responses comprised between the extremes of conventional laminate configurations at $E_i = 6$ J (see Table 3), at $E_i = 25$ J relevant differences were detected (Table 4). All IGIS laminates

showed peak loads higher than the COMP one (with performance gains from 12 % to 27 %, and HCNC even better performing than the NEAT laminate). HNC, HNCN and HX samples showed peak displacements comparable to COMP but higher recovered energies (9.1 J, 8.2 J and 9.3 J respectively). HCN and HCNC laminates showed the lowest peak displacements and the highest recovered energies (+37 % for both configurations with respect to the COMP one), with Load versus Displacement curves without any apparent signal of fibre breakage (and displacement at peak load almost coinciding with the peak displacement). These latter two IGIS configurations exhibited a sound improvement over the compatibilized laminate impact performances and were able to preserve the integrity of reinforcing fibres.

Sample	Peak Load (N)	Peak Displacement (mm)	Absorbed Energy (J)	Recovered Energy (J)	Residual Displacement (mm)
NEAT	8035±176	5.8±0.3	15.1±0.2	10.1±0.2	1.4±0.1
COMP	6631±92	5.9±0.1	17.7±0.2	7.5±0.2	1.1±0.1
HNC	7432±154	5.8±0.3	16.1±0.2	9.1±0.2	1.1±0.1
HCN	7506±108	5.7±0.2	14.9±0.2	10.3±0.2	1.3±0.1
HNCN	7951±143	5.8±0.2	17.3±0.2	8.2±0.2	1.1±0.1
HCNC	8437±164	5.6±0.2	14.9±0.2	10.3±0.2	1.1±0.1
HX	8055±204	5.8±0.3	15.9±0.2	9.3±0.2	1.3±0.1

Table 4 Average value and variance of main parameters evaluated from impact tests performed at 25 J

Figure 3 Load versus displacement curves from low velocity impact tests as a function of the stacking sequence: A) Impact energy = 6J, B) Impact Energy = 25J.

Figure 4 Energy versus Time curves obtained from low velocity impact tests as a function of the stacking sequence: A) Impact energy = 6J, B) Impact Energy = 25J.

The high values of recovered energy coupled with the absence of fibre breakage indicated that the matrix layering of HCN and HCNC can withstand much higher impact loads before the composite

failure with respect to the conventional compatibilized laminate configuration (COMP). The HCN interlaminar interface strength configuration revealed the best overall performances among all IGIS designs but its asymmetric configuration can be used only if a preferential static or impact load direction can be identified, otherwise in case of symmetric loads the HX design could be the most suitable layering. The detected impact performances of IGIS laminates highlighted that the use of the interlaminar gradation of the interface strength could be a very effective method to improve the damage resistance of thermoplastic composites without heavily affecting the static flexural performances.

3.3 Flexural properties

Due to the high inclination of composite materials to impact damage, dramatic loss in residual strength and in structural integrity results. Residual strengths in tension, compression, bending and fatigue will be reduced to varying degrees depending on the dominant damage mode. In order to obtain a better indication of the damage tolerance, which indicates a system's ability to perform post-impact, the normalized flexural strength (or stiffness) of each specimen is evaluated as the ratio of the mean strength (or stiffness) of the impacted specimen to the mean value of the flexural strength (or stiffness) of the undamaged specimen. Figure 5A and Figure 5B show the normalized flexural strength and stiffness as a function of increasing impact energy, respectively, whilst Table 5 summarizes the flexural properties of the laminates.

It can be clearly seen that the best performances in terms of both strength and stiffness are obtained for fully compatibilized composites (COMP), thus highlighting the positive role played by the coupling agent. As a general comment, all composites suffered from failures in the compression side that occurred at different stresses as a function of the interface strength. In this regard, NEAT composites offered the lowest performance due to the absence of significant stress-transfer at the fibre/matrix interface.

Specimen	Flexural strength (MPa)	Flexural modulus (GPa)	Flexural strength (MPa)	Flexural modulus (GPa)	Flexural strength (MPa)	Flexural modulus (GPa)
	Non-impacted		Impact Energy: 6 J		Impact Energy: 25 J	
NEAT	115.88±3.38	16.49±0.85	103.27±3.36	14.92±0.24	86.33±3.37	13.27±0.39
COMP	192.11±7.42	20.92±0.32	178.09±5.20	20.04±0.84	154.09±1.63	17.14±0.19
HNC	116.47±1.32	17.08±1.28	110.00±4.15	16.67±0.17	92.26±2.89	12.3±0.63
HCN	175.42±2.24	20.51±0.69	167.18±3.58	19.08±0.36	150.32±1.92	18.13±0.51
HNCN	145.65±3.56	19.23±0.87	138.51±2.49	17.58±0.49	112.33±2.09	12.62±0.42
HCNC	164.74±2.86	16.87±0.29	134.17±2.73	15.78±0.53	121.31±2.28	15.18±0.34
HX	134.48±3.08	15.79±0.47	117.63±3.06	15.25±0.12	107.8±2.67	13.36±0.29

Table 5 Summary of flexural properties for thermoplastic-based composites

Figure 5 Normalized residual flexural strength (A) and modulus (B) as a function of impact energy

The increasing trend of damaging for all laminates caused by low velocity impacts is matched by the reduction of the flexural strength and, to a greater extent, of the flexural modulus. Interface strength gradation proved to be a valuable approach to enhance the mechanical properties of thermoplastic-based composites, especially as regards the damage tolerance. All the configurations can be ranked from the higher to the lower flexural strength in the following order: HCN>COMP,

HX>HNC>HNCN>NEAT>HCNC. As a general conclusion, with increasing impact energy, the best compromise in terms of both quasi-static properties and damage tolerance appears to be the HCN configuration. These results can be linked to the different mechanisms responsible for energy dissipation and the development of damage during subsequent flexural loading that is known to introduce a complex stress pattern in the specimen. Therefore the effect of the damage on residual strength is less easy to analyse and to this purpose the time evolution of different failure modes was studied through the analysis of acoustic emission signals.

3.4 Acoustic emission analysis

AE events amplitude and duration distributions for undamaged and impacted samples are reported in Table 6. Figure 6 shows a comparison of the damage modes found in laminates at the end of flexural tests. For NEAT composites, all the damage is concentrated on the compression side and only at 25J the failure tends to be localized and the impact damage seems to prevail over flexural loading. From AE analysis, no signals of high amplitude (>75 dB) [15–17] were detected, thus highlighting the low occurrence of fibre failures that can be responsible of the low strength offered by such composites. Most AE signals are in the ranges 35-50 dB and 0-50 μ s for amplitude and duration, respectively, which are usually ascribed to matrix cracking. These signals are reasonably located in the most critical zone that is the compression side of the specimens.

	<i>Impact Energy</i>	<i>0J</i>		<i>6J</i>		<i>25J</i>		
		<i>Range*</i>	<i>Amplitude (dB)</i>	<i>Duration (μs)</i>	<i>Amplitude (dB)</i>	<i>Duration (μs)</i>	<i>Amplitude (dB)</i>	<i>Duration (μs)</i>
NEAT	1		86.49	80.31	83.72	82.47	84.32	76.66
	2		12.98	16.64	15.87	14.23	15.01	19.55
	3		0.51	2.37	0.4	2.41	0.67	2.95
	4		0.02	0.35	0.01	0.44	-	0.42
	5		-	0.33	-	0.45	-	0.42
HCN	1		82.15	85.18	60.94	69.89	53.03	64.22
	2		17.09	9.69	33.59	21.1	36.72	24.34
	3		0.76	3.85	3.43	3.02	8.12	6.66
	4		-	0.67	0.03	2	0.13	1.66
	5		-	0.62	2.01	3.99	2	3.12
HNC	1		85.2	84.27	57.9	69.9	64.12	71.75
	2		14.52	8.13	37.78	16.32	34	15.11
	3		0.24	2.46	4.28	3.7	1.82	4.3
	4		0.03	1.84	0.02	3.35	0.05	2.96
	5		0.01	3.3	0.02	6.73	0.01	5.88
COMP	1		87.38	68.44	58.73	59.72	60.11	56.29
	2		12.45	17.78	33.82	13.01	32.59	24.63
	3		0.14	4.02	3.37	6.54	3.24	4.78
	4		0.02	3.2	2.07	9.95	2.05	4.32
	5		0.01	6.56	2.01	10.78	2.01	9.98
HNCN	1		80.32	84.63	90.57	88.3	48.16	61.4
	2		17.55	13.79	9.41	10.11	43.67	28.01
	3		2.13	0.81	0.02	1.15	8.1	4.11
	4		-	0.34	-	0.22	0.07	2.07
	5		-	0.43	-	0.22	-	4.41
HCNC	1		88.12	73.43	68.98	67.83	61.54	61.27
	2		11.68	15.73	29.83	15.24	34.59	21.75
	3		0.16	3.39	1.15	5.31	3.8	5.67
	4		0.02	2.49	0.02	3.66	0.05	3.55
	5		0.02	4.96	0.02	7.96	0.02	7.76
HX	1		66.42	63.9	64.31	55.17	55.82	52.42
	2		31.2	16.24	31.7	17.27	35.11	18.76
	3		2.34	6.74	3.95	10.04	8.94	9.49
	4		0.02	4.81	0.04	8.41	0.13	9.77
	5		0.02	6.31	-	9.11	-	9.56

*Range for amplitude: 1) 35-45 dB; 2) 45-55 dB; 3) 55-65 dB; 4) 65-75 dB; 5) 75-100 dB

*Range for duration: 1) 0-50 μ s; 2) 50-100 μ s; 3) 100-150 μ s; 4) 150-200 μ s; 5) >200 μ s

Table 6 Relative distribution (%) of amplitude and duration of AE signals

Figure 6 Damage modes observed in laminates once failed in bending

With increasing impact energy, there is a slight increase in signals of medium amplitude and duration (intervals 2 and 3). This can be an indication of the absence of extensive delaminations to absorb impact energy. Isolated interfacial failures and matrix microcracking linked to failure in compression side (fibre microbuckling and kink bands) appear to be the main mechanisms responsible for the absorption of impact energy. This could explain the relatively low energy absorption at 25 J.

Specimens with asymmetric matrix stacking sequence (HCN and HNC) exhibited different behaviours for both static and dynamic loading with HCN outperforming HNC configuration. Up to 6J the failure of HCN laminates is still characterized by a failure in the compression side even though at 25J the failure reached also the tensile side. The better behaviour can be ascribed to the fact that the compression side is compatibilized and therefore offers a greater strength. AE analysis revealed an increased number of signals of amplitude and duration belonging to the second and third interval that can be ascribed to interface failures with increasing impact energy, thus moving the overall failure from the compression to the tensile side. There is also evidence of signals related to fibre breakages due to the effect of compatibilizing agent. The better damage tolerance seems to be the result of a delay in failure of the compression side due to the presence of a stronger interface adhesion. HNC configuration was found to offer inferior static and damage tolerance properties compared to HCN layering sequence due to the presence of a non compatibilized zone in the critical compression side. Compared to HCN, there are more signals of higher duration that indicate the development of extensive delaminations, which are responsible for the higher absorption of energy for this configuration. COMP laminates exhibited an acceptable damage tolerance and AE signature was characterized by the presence of signals pointing to extensive fibre breakages that trigger delaminations diffused in the whole volume of the specimens that can absorb high amount of impact energy.

Laminates with symmetric interface strength highlighted the positive role played by the compatibilized core (HNCN). In this case the AE signals up to 6J are concentrated in the lower ranges for both amplitude and duration due to a diffused matrix microcracking. With increasing impact energy, the behaviour resembles the one found for COMP laminates with a lower occurrence of signals amplitude and duration, thus suggesting an increasing damage (interface failures and microcracks) in the non-compatibilized skins. The presence of a non-compatibilized core (HCNC) is responsible for the lower damage tolerance compared to HNCN laminates. For HCNC composites, there was an increasing number of AE signals with increasing impact energy due to the failure of non-compatibilized core. The significant number of signals detected as a function of impact energy can be ascribed to diffused damages that coalesce to become critical for the core that, once failed, triggers the failure of the tensile side. The HX configuration exhibited the highest number of AE signals among the configurations investigated, thus highlighting the presence of a diffused damage due to the several interfaces present in the layering sequence. Damage partition among internal interfaces enables HX laminates, although less resistant than HCNC and HNCN, to show a lower degradation of their strength at higher impact energies. Also in this case the failure was a mixed compression-tensile mode.

For a general conclusion about the previous results, it may be inferred that disposing a non-compatibilized core between two compatibilized skins provides in principle better static strength but lower damage tolerance to low velocity impacts. For impact energies approaching penetration, more complex layering sequences, involving intercalated compatibilized and non-compatibilized matrix layers, such as in HX laminates, may offer better predictability of impact damage propagation in composites and higher residual properties.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Hybrid thermoplastic composites based on polypropylene and glass fibre woven fabrics were prepared according to a new hybridization technique. The new design was based on the gradation of the interlaminar interface strength (IGIS). IGIS laminates were prepared by properly alternating layers of compatibilized or not compatibilized polypropylene films in symmetric or asymmetric sequences, without affecting the reinforcement configuration.

In conventional composites, the presence of the coupling agent increases the capability to transfer loads from the matrix to the fibres. This results in improved flexural modulus and, to a higher extent,

flexural strength but in decreased low velocity impact resistance, leading to fibres breakage and lower recovery of the elastic energy. The reduced interface strength in not compatibilized composites allows the occurrence of fibres pull-out phenomena which dissipate a high amount of energy through sliding mechanisms and friction between fibres and matrix.

The IGIS design allows to prepare composites with high flexural properties coupled with high impact resistance without affecting the reinforcement configuration nor using fibre hybridization methods. IGIS laminates exhibited static flexural properties comprised between those of fully neat and fully compatibilized composites. One configuration (HCN) showed a flexural response quite close to that of the compatibilized laminate. The low velocity impact characterization, performed at 6 J and 25 J, demonstrated that grading the matrix/fibres interface strength can be an effective way to retain good mechanical properties while allowing significant increases in the impact damage tolerance. In fact, IGIS configurations showed no or limited damaging of fibres. Among all configurations the HCN one exhibited the highest peak load and the highest recovered energy, outperforming the composites based on compatibilized and not compatibilized PP.

Acoustic emission monitoring of post-impact flexural tests offered some insights into the development of damage and confirmed the favourable balance of static and damage tolerance properties of the asymmetric matrix stacking sequence (HCN). In addition, due to the highest number of AE signals among the configurations investigated ascribed to a diffused damage, the intercalated stacking sequence proved to be a suitable damage tolerance material with increasing impact energy.

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